

Investigating the Position of Independent Media in Afghanistan from the Interim Administration to the National Unity Government

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Abstract

In fact, element of progress and development of communities is considered the key emancipation of nations from domination and dependence, As well as the development of foundations of society is a tool for strengthening of constant peace and stability, which nations are always in need of it. The nations in one hand, do not develop until they can stand on their feet, and on the other hand until they don't stand up on their feet, they don't have significant look within themselves, and they will not develop. Medias and Mass Communications play an essential role in the development of the country because it facilitate dealings and makes it possible to transfer information and knowledge. Years of war and conflict which is still going on, have inflicted severe damages for Afghanistan in various fields. After the collapse of Taliban regime and the attendance of United Nations, democracy, liberated media and uplifting them were the prime policy of government and United Nations, and these concerted efforts have resulted in establishment of the private Medias, party Medias and government Medias had conspicuous development. Democracy and freedom of Media's activity were one of the important merits that not only United Nations, but also the Afghan governors confess. Recently, in circumstance of democracy, composition and establishment of media in Afghanistan and the challenges that the media community had faced, many articles have published and all of them were focused about one of the yyybig problems in Afghanistan (Media and Communication). In this research, points, such as estate of establishment and development of media and also profitability of their activities has been discussed.

Keywords: Interim Administration, Media and national unity government, Democracy, Freedom of Media's, United Nations, Development of media, Establishment of Media.

Introduction

Research Goal

In this article, the following objectives will be studied.

- 1- Exploring how different Medias are created and developed in the country, which is one of the important goals of this research.
2. Understanding the relationship between media creation and the needs of Afghan society and their position is another purpose of this article.
- 3 - Another purpose of this study is to understand the relationship between how the mass media develops in Afghan society.

Research Methods

In this research, both the library method and the field method, particularly interviews and questionnaires (survey) are implemented. In this way, I can answer the main and sub-questions of this research in order to achieve the goals of this research successfully.

The Importance of Research

The media world has been a unique world in human history, and never in the history of human life has the media witnessed such dynamic and rapid change because communication technology has not only made the world smaller, it has made every day a different day, and by describing the features of the media world, we can better understand its importance.

The mass media have a wide context, they reach the depths of the masses, and it can be rightly said that no element like the media can penetrate the depths of society. The media pervades society and there is no area that is not in the light of their waves. The breadth of media work has many consequences.

In the light of the age of communication, traditional institutions have taken on new dimensions, for example, home is no longer a place to eat and sleep, but beyond the media, the home is a place of study and development in human life and thought. Although there are views, it seems that the media is also a source of addiction. As we still see this well in our daily lives.

At the cultural level, the media led to the opening of closed cultures and the gradual realization of cultural integration at the local and global levels. The individual is no longer belongs to a particular language or tribe. The closed tribes are opened, the walls of closed cultures are

penetrated, and finally, the intersection of ideas has taken place, and national identity, national language, thoughts and beliefs of the whole society instead. The place of society has penetrated, which can cause wide-ranging changes at the macro level of society.

Therefore, the functional importance of the media caused the mass media to be created one after the other, after the fall of the Taliban regime in the country, and with the efforts of journalists and writers in the country, this field has grown significantly.

Undoubtedly, the creation of the media has helped to create a sense of citizenship and good governance. How the media has grown and what has been the position and efficiency of the media during this period, is an important issue that is the issue of this article.

Background Research

Unfortunately, no significant work has been done in this regard so far. It is not enough and it requires more exploration be done in this field by the researchers of the country in order to cause the cultural load of the country.

Research Questions

A) The main question

1- How do you think the work of the media has been useful and efficient in the country?

B) Sub-questions

1- Has the media been able to create a suitable mental space in the axis of accurate and appropriate political programs?

2. How did the media feel about the people?

3- Has the consensus and orientation of the media on various issues of the country been in the interests of all the people of the country?

Research Hypothesis

The political tendencies of the people in Afghanistan are based on ethnic and personal axes, and the media could not create a suitable mental atmosphere in the axis of accurate and appropriate political programs.

Theoretical Foundations of Research

The press in a democratic system, Anis and McLuhan recognized the media as the essence of civilizations, and both believe that history is driven by the dominant media in every age. (Noorbakhsh, 415 p. 1392).

Freedom of expression and information is a fundamental human right. The holy religion of Islam condemns the dissemination of false material and information, as well as the unwillingness to tell the truth, which implies not only freedom of speech, but also the responsibility of telling the truth. The Holy Quran states: "And do not confuse the right with the wrong, and do not conceal the knowledge of the truth" (Quran 2: 2 4). "O you, who believe! Always stand up for God, and bear witness to justice, do not be hostile to the people, lead you to sin and forsake justice, do justice that is closer to piety, and avoid the sin of God, which is what You do, it is news! (Holy Quran: 5-8).

The biggest national pact of freedom of expression in our country is the Afghan Constitution. Article 34 of the Afghan Constitution recognizes the right to freedom of expression in the following words: "Freedom of expression is inviolable.

Every Afghan has the right to express his opinion through speech, writing, images or other means, in accordance with the provisions of this law. Every Afghan has the right, in accordance with the law, to publish material without first submitting it to government officials. Rulings on press, radio and television, press publishing and other mass media are regulated by law (Ministry of Justice, Constitution, p. 18).

The issue of media freedom has been fully explored and rethought. What faces an unprecedented challenge today is not just the issue of media freedom; rather, the basic rights of the citizen are in the field of information and communication (Mehdi, 2012, pp. 4-6).

International law and human rights law, in particular Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, guarantee freedom of expression. In global culture, the word "freedom of expression" refers to the protection and advocacy of any activity of obtaining, obtaining or communicating information or ideas, regardless of which language is used. Thus, freedom of expression includes cultural and artistic expression, the exchange of information, ideas and political debate. For a political system that experiences true democracy must have the right to freedom of expression and its true meaning, the exchange of ideas, ideas and information must be considered a general practice and not limited to private conversations. (Poudy Pat, 2006 p. 54).

Thus, the media helps to understand common values, values and concerns by providing opportunities to build an ideal society, in the field of democratic nation-building, in the creation and development of different political, social and civic institutions. The media continue to institutionalize the culture of democracy, which can lead to the survival of democratic institutions

in the country. This is why democrats resist any attempt to encroach on the independence of journalists or to try to impose ideological goals, even if they are ideological and valuable (Kern, James Shantwingar, 2009, p. 17). - 20).

As noted above, freedom of expression lays the foundation for an environment in which both individuals and undoubtedly competing political parties can freely engage in their party activities, as well as freedom of expression for civil society. Informs political leaders and other social institutions and paves the way for comments and opinions on public policies that in turn strengthen and enhance the quality of government work (Toril, Petralist, and James Alberg, 2010, p. 259). -265).

However, it should be said that the freedom of the media is always in line with their social responsibilities, so the mission of the media is to lead society towards unity and integrity, social justice and public welfare. Prevent slander, insults and inviting people to riot because the publication and distribution of news, information, false statements, biased (Nabeel, 2, 3). Propaganda, provocative rumors, which are intended to disrupt security, create fear and panic among the people or to the detriment of the public interest, on the one hand, the media has bad consequences for itself. On the other, it leads the society to misery (Nabeel, 2012, pp. 15-18).

How Create Media in the Country (Afghanistan)

After 2002, the interim administration came to power until the end of the second term of the presidency (2014), Afghanistan experienced freedom of expression by publishing and establishing free media. All political forces have used the media as a weapon in their political struggles, and even the Taliban have begun making videos and launching websites to get their message across.

The significant increase in the media in the country may have been one of the greatest achievements of the Afghan government and the efforts of the international community over the years, said Siddiqullah Tawhidi, head of the Media Watch, in an interview with BNA (Thursday, May 5, 2012, 08:16). The role of electronic media, i.e. .radio and television, has been significant in these thirteen years.

Din Mohammad Mobarez Rashedi, former Deputy Minister of Publications of the Ministry of Information and Culture in the second cabinet of President Karzai, said in an interview with the Bakhtar Information Agency (Thursday, May 5, 2012, 08:16). "Freedom of expression in Afghanistan has been one of the most important and pioneering areas for the growth of Afghanistan

and it can be said that the greatest achievement of the people and government of Afghanistan has been with the help of the international community over the years."Speech in Afghanistan has created the conditions for the people to have their say in the government of men and to participate in determining their own destiny," Rashedi said. Today, there are about 150 radios, fifty televisions, 14 newspapers and more than fifteen news agencies in the country.

According to Rashedi, in the past, national radio and television were really the mouthpiece of governments. Regimes covered their weaknesses with this television and told the Afghan people what they wanted, but for now, national television or state media, like the free media, must follow a single law called the Afghan Public Media Law, but in practice national radio and television still act as government speakers in some cases. According to Rashedi, the working agenda of the state media consists of the publication of development and progress programs related to the government of Afghanistan. But censorship, lying and concealment are not part of their agenda, which should not be the case.

"The current situation of the media in the country is a great booty," said Syed Makhdoom Raheen, Afghanistan's Minister of Information and Culture in Karzai's second cabinet, in an interview with Radio Deutsche Welle. "It is claimed that the international community and the Afghan government have not done anything in the last ten years, but in his view this judgment is far from fair because a lot has been done over the years," he said.

An example is the development and multiplicity of Afghan private media in this regard. As he mentioned that Afghanistan has never experienced such media pluralism, freedom and progress in media affairs, and this multiplicity may be due to the simplification of legal provisions regarding the creation of media in the country (Amin Behzad, 3).

Shah Hussein Mortazavi, a journalist and deputy spokesman for the president in Kabul, also confirmed the developments, saying that they have educational shortcomings (Amin Behzad, 3).

According to Bawer-e-man, the existence of diverse and critical media, after the overthrow of the Taliban regime in Afghanistan in 2001, has diversified the country's political arena, which in most cases has led to reform and regulation of affairs, especially around the direction of misleading public opinion during this period. Of course, while institutionalizing the culture of freedom of expression, the media have been able to greatly contribute to strengthening the shaky foundations of the fledgling democratic system in Afghanistan.

The Afghan Public Media Law, adopted by the House of Representatives in 2009, regulates Article 19 of the International Covenant on Human Rights, which emphasizes the right to freedom of expression and thought. Intended to create a medium. The law states that Those who want to establish a media outlet must be over 18 years old and a citizen of the country, and also not be deprived of civil activities by a court (Zafarshah Royi, 2).

Considering the simple and easy conditions for creating a media in Afghanistan led to the creation of hundreds of media in Afghanistan, it can be estimated that nearly one thousand video, audio and print media by the Ministry of Information and Culture of Afghanistan since 2001. They have obtained an activity license. Unfortunately, many of them have not been able to continue their activities due to financial problems.

The new press law has the slightest advantage over previous laws in removing radio and television from government monopoly and allowing the Afghan private sector and citizens to set up radio, television and film companies. (Radiation, 1).

Tawhidi, head of media watchdog at the Inter News Center in Kabul, believes that the content of Afghanistan's media has been improving throughout history and that the media has been able to influence the minds of the people. He stated that the Afghan people had just gained confidence in their domestic media; But the media critical of the government was more encouraging to the people.

"Some print and electronic media outlets have made the necessary efforts to improve their content and standardize their activities. Their work is improving day by day, month by month and year by year, and there is hope that in the future, we will "We have standard media with good content compared to today." "Afghanistan's media has grown significantly in recent years and now seventy-six percent of the population trusts the media," said Jen Miktor, director of the Internews Institute in Kabul. Which is a good relationship between the people and the government, which shows the growth of media work in this period (Zafarshah Royi, 2).

Afghan publishers believe that during this period, Afghanistan has witnessed the most important cultural change. As some of these publishers and authors say: Afghanistan had never published a book as widely as it does today. Mohammad Nabi Sharafiar, an Afghan writer and president of the National Union of Publishers and Booksellers of Afghanistan, said that hundreds of books have been published in this country in the last decade. The expansion of cultural activities in the country also boosted the work of the press.

According to Din Mohammad Mobarez Rashedi, Deputy Minister of Publications of the Ministry of Information and Culture, 500 printing houses have been licensed in this ministry so far. According to him, the number of printing houses may be more than this because it is possible that some printing houses also operate without a license (former).

The development of media work in Afghanistan over the last decade has been fraught with many challenges and problems. One of these challenges has been the lack of experience in media work in this country. However, for the first time, the country's media have been able to be good sources of information for their people. Tawhidi, head of media watchdog at the institute, said that "Although the Afghan media has not yet acted in accordance with international norms and standards and has not reached international standards, but the way they have taken is to hope that the work of the media in Afghanistan will be standardized." (Previous).

Report Research Results

In this research, 50 questionnaires were distributed to the students, , educated people of different ages in numerous provinces of Afghanistan ,such as Kabul, Parwan, Kapisa, Panjshir and Badakhshan and the results are as follows:

Test the Research hypothesis

1-Do you think that the political tendencies of the people in Afghanistan have been based on ethnic and personal axes?

A - Too much B - Much C - Medium D. Bad E -Too bad

In terms of number:

A-28 person B-16 person C-6 person D- zero E-zero

In percentage terms:

A-56% B- 32% C- 12% D- 0% E- 0%

2- Can the media create a suitable mental atmosphere in accurate and appropriate political programs in the past years?

A - Too much B - Much C - Medium D- Bad d - Too bad

In terms of number:

A-8 person B-10 person C-29 person D-3 person E-zero

In percentage terms:

A-16% B-20% C-58% D-6% E-0%

3- How has the media felt about the people?

A - Excellent B - Good C - Medium D - Bad E - Very bad

In terms of number:

10 person B-12 person C-19 person D-6 person E- 3 person

In percentage terms:

A-20% B-24% C- 38% D-12% E- 6%

4- How much do you think the work of the media has been useful and efficient?

A- Excellent B- Good C- Medium D- Bad E - Very bad

In terms of number:

A-12 person B-20 person C-12 person D-5 person E-1 person

In percentage terms:

A-24% B- 40% C- 24% D- 10% E-2%

5- Has the consensus and orientation of the media on various issues of the country been in the interests of all people?

A- Excellent B- Good C- Medium D- Bad E - Very bad

In terms of number:

A-6 person B-10 person C-22 person D-10 person E-2 person

In percentage terms:

A-12% B- 20% C- 44% D- 20% E- 4%

Conflict

The historical course of media activity in the country shows that there have been many ups and downs in the way of media work and activity in the country, as sometimes the media have published normally and sometimes their publications have been stopped due to the current national policies. As I wrote in my previous work entitled (Study of media systems in Afghanistan), this means that the political history of the country has not inherited the normal process of media activity

for us. With the emergence of a new political atmosphere in the country, the media had a good and appropriate growth in terms of quantity, but in terms of quality, they still face certain challenges.

The Holy Quran considers freedom of expression and information to be a fundamental human right and condemns the dissemination of false information as well as the unwillingness to state the truth, which implies not only freedom of expression but also the responsibility of truthfulness.

As Allah says: "And do not confuse the right with the wrong and do not hide knowing the right." Our greatest national pact is the Constitution, which recognizes freedom of expression in Article 34. In the fourth article of the second chapter of the Law on Public Rights and Obligations, the Law on Public Media states in this regard: "Everyone has the right to freedom of thought and expression, and in the second paragraph of the same article states: The government protects, strengthens and guarantees freedom of expression.

International law and human rights law, especially Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, also guarantee freedom of expression. Sayed Morteza Noorbakhsh in his book *Basic Concepts of Communication Knowledge* on page 415 states that McLuhan's first ideas about the media were based on the work of his experienced and trusted friend, Harold Adams, Anis. Anis and McLuhan recognize the media as the essence of civilization, and both believe that history is driven by the dominant media in every age.

Therefore, all scientists have somehow referred directly or indirectly to the social responsibilities of the media, and I also come to the conclusion in this debate that the media must respect their social responsibility, and in this way it is also beneficial for the intellectual growth of society. They happen and have a good return for the people, something that the country's media have shown less competence in these cases during this period.

Conclusion

As a result, it can be said that a number of publications in this period were not based on a social, cultural or political necessity; rather, the issue of creating jobs for several people and more for the responsible manager has been raised, perhaps because most of the media in this period suffered from content lessness and thought that one media is a repetition of another media.

However in this period while speaking of freedom of expression; Human rights and a free press are at stake, and Afghan journalists are more threatened than ever. Perhaps one of the reasons for this is that criticism is more partisan than constructive. It is expected that in the press of this period, constructive and scientific plans related to the modernization of Afghanistan were presented, which, however, are less likely to be seen in the current press. In Afghanistan, the press still suffers from absolutism. In most journals, according to their graders, the good are always absolutely good and the bad are absolutely bad (Partaw Naderi, 1).

Another challenge of the media work of this period is that the media has acted more in the way of eliminating the opposition than accepting them.). It should also be noted that in this period, the language of many publications is not in line with grammatical criteria and writing norms. In addition to this problem, the increasing and increasing use of foreign words and terms in the country's media can face serious difficulties and problems in the future of Dari and Pashto Persian language and literature.

Considering and evaluating the activity of the country's media, it can be claimed that in addition to the problems that plague the country's media, such as not coming out of ethnic publications, unpreparedness to leave the transition to a stable stage of professional media publications, unprepared Gay can be recalled for creating and designing publishing programs to meet the needs of the community. Although, unfortunately, sometimes "our media has not acted on the basis of its professional responsibilities, which in itself has caused people to be pessimistic about the work of the media in this period." The media evaluated it well during this period, although it may not have been equal to the expectations of our people, but it can be said that the government with the media is better than the government without the media.

On the other hand, the mass media in our country has had a very good effect on the mental and intellectual development of the people during this period, although, as we said, the media have had serious problems in terms of content; However, it is fortunate that the media has to some extent caused the intellectual growth of the country's citizens.

Suggestions

By considering the effects of the media on society, the following suggestions can be made in order to improve the affairs of society:

1. Fortunately, during this period, the policy of the national development strategy of the country has been prepared. This policy determines the perspective of the activity and the path of progress in the country, but what needs to be noted is that the country's top leaders must respect this strategy and pursue it along with the national policy and interests of all Afghans. The design and implementation of any program far from the interests of all the people of Afghanistan behind the black glasses of prejudice will cause the misery of the people. Unfortunately, during this period, no serious efforts were made to become a nation and unite the people, and the intellectuals of all ethnic groups, including the top leaders in the system, sought hypocrisy instead of unity.
2. To regulate the affairs of society in all sectors, especially the media, it is necessary to think nationally and act nationally. Any action and thought based on ethnic, regional, group and regional tastes causes the collapse of the foundations of national and private institutions in the country. Becomes. Most of the media in the country are run either by parties or by individuals and ethnic leaders, by designing and pursuing a clear national policy and avoiding tribal politics in the country, can build national trust, which is national trust. It can create opportunities for becoming a nation. Because the experience of these years has shown that most of our problems are due to the same blind ethnic, linguistic, group and regional policies.
3. One of the issues that needed to be addressed was the seriousness of the media criticism by the Government of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan and its response to these criticisms, which were not taken into account at all.
4. The media should follow the criticism they raise.
5. The country's media should come out of ethnocentric publications, and should take the initiative, and start reforming themselves both in terms of publishing programs and in terms of administrative organization.
6. The government should ensure the job security of journalists and act against the media in accordance with the principle of observing the rights and professional ethics of media work in exposing corruption and creating accountability in accordance with the law on the right of access to information in developing and reforming governance affairs.

7. The Government of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan should support journalists by pursuing reasonable policies, especially in relation to the work and professional immunity of media employees.

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